

A New Lanthanum Vanadium Bronze

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Manuscript Received 15 March 1975 ; revised 23 April 1975 ; accepted 19 May 1975

A new bronze type phase of composition $\text{La}_{0.1}\text{V}_2\text{O}_5$ is obtained by the solid state reaction between La_2O_3 , VO_2 and V_2O_5 at 750° for 24 hr in evacuated sealed silica tube. The bronze type compound is characterized by X-ray diffraction, electrical conductivity, seebeck coefficient, magnetic susceptibility and EPR studies. It is isostructural with other known β -type vanadium bronzes of the general formula $\text{M}_x\text{V}_2\text{O}_5$, where M is usually a monovalent metal. Electrical conductivity and magnetic studies indicate the localized character of conduction electrons at V^{4+} sites. The Seebeck coefficient data show the small polaron nature of the charge carriers.

TRANSITION metal oxygen bronzes are nonstoichiometric compounds formed by the insertion of a metal M into the covalent lattice of the transition metal oxides, TO_n (WO_3 , MoO_3 and V_2O_5 etc.). The bronzes exhibit interesting structural, electrical and magnetic properties. It has been found¹⁻⁴ that the M atoms, placed in the tunnels of the oxide matrix, undergo ionization transferring its valence electrons to the oxide network thereby reducing a corresponding amount of the transition metal ion, T^{2n+} to lower valence state. The structure and physical properties of these bronzes depend mainly on the structure of the parent transition metal oxide, the extent of insertion of the metal M , and the nature of the electrons transferred from M to T . The transferred electrons may be either collective or localized depending on the covalent interaction between T^{2n+} and O^{2-} in the parent oxide. Thus, the tungsten bronzes are metallic conductors with weak temperature independent Pauli paramagnetism while the vanadium bronzes are semiconductors exhibiting Curie-Weiss paramagnetic behaviour.

Phase diagram studies on the three component systems $\text{M}_2\text{O}-\text{V}_2\text{O}_5-\text{VO}_2$ ($M = \text{Li}, \text{Na}, \text{Ag}$)⁴⁻⁶ have established the occurrence of the following phases.

Subsequently, Wadsley⁷ determined the crystal structures of both $\beta\text{-M}_x\text{V}_2\text{O}_5$ and $\text{M}_{1+y}\text{V}_3\text{O}_8$ phases, which inspired further work on the physical properties of these bronzes. Studies on the α and ν phases are relatively few while $\beta\text{-M}_x\text{V}_2\text{O}_5$ bronzes have been investigated widely. $\beta\text{-M}_x\text{V}_2\text{O}_5$ ($M = \text{Li}, \text{Na}, \text{Ag}, \text{Cu}$)^{1-4, 8-10} bronzes are reported to crystallize in monoclinic system. This fairly complex structure is built up of highly distorted V-O polyhedra by sharing faces and corners. In this structure, vanadium ions are found both in distorted trigonal bipyramidal and octahedral oxygen coordination. The structure gives rise to zig-zag tunnels parallel to b axis which are interlinked at suitable intervals. The inserted metal atoms are placed in these tunnels. The electrical conduction in single crystals of the bronzes along the tunnel axis is higher than that along the perpendicular direction at least by three order of magnitude¹¹.

Recently, we have reported¹² the preparation and physical properties of an ammonium vanadium bronze, $(\text{NH}_4)_x\text{V}_2\text{O}_5$.

Comparing the ionic size and electropositive nature of alkali and alkaline earth metals with those of lanthanide elements (ionization potential values), one would expect the formation of lanthanum vanadium bronzes also to occur. In this connection, it may be noted that recently Ln_xWO_3 bronzes have been prepared and studied by Ostertag¹³. In the present paper, the preparation of $\text{La}_x\text{V}_2\text{O}_5$ and its characterization by X-ray diffraction, electrical conductivity, Seebeck coefficient, magnetic susceptibility, and EPR measurements are reported.

Experimental

La_2O_3 (>99.9%) and V_2O_5 (>99.9%) used in this work were supplied by Indian Rare Earths Limited and Reanal, Hungary, respectively. All other chemicals employed were of BDH AnalaR grade.

In a preliminary investigation, La_2O_3 and V_2O_5 were mixed in the mole ratio 1 : 20. The mixture was taken to the molten condition ($\sim 750^\circ$) and then slowly cooled to room temperature in air. During cooling, evolution (or 'spitting') of oxygen was observed yielding a shiny black bronze-like crystalline phase at the surface. The substance at the surface layer, on analysis, indicated the presence of V^{4+} proportional to the amount of La_2O_3 added. This revealed the insertion of lanthanum atoms into V_2O_5 matrix and consequent reduction of V^{5+} to V^{4+} , to form an impure bronze phase.

The preparation of pure $\text{La}_x\text{V}_2\text{O}_5$ phases with $0.05 \leq x \leq 0.15$ was achieved by heating at 750°C for 24 hours appropriate quantities of La_2O_3 , VO_2 and V_2O_5 in sealed evacuated silica tubes. The total vanadium and lower valence vanadium in the product estimated by the potentiometric method described earlier¹² were as follows :

	Found %	Calculated for $\text{La}_{0.1}^3\text{V}_{0.30}^4\text{V}_{1.70}^5\text{O}_5$ (%)
V^{4+}	7.90	7.80
Total V	51.61	52.02

X-ray powder diffraction patterns of the bronzes were recorded using Zr-filtered MoK α radiation. Magnetic susceptibility, electrical conductivity and Seebeck coefficient measurements were made for the polycrystalline samples using apparatuses similar to those described by Rao and coworkers^{12,14,15}. Electron spin resonance spectrum of the polycrystalline sample was recorded at room temperature using a Varian E-4 EPR spectrometer.

Results and Discussion

Bronze phases with small amounts of lanthanum content (La_{0.05}V₂O₅) give X-ray diffraction patterns very similar to that of V₂O₅ indicating perhaps the formation of α -La_xV₂O₅. In these patterns, the characteristic lines of La₂O₃ and VO₂ are absent, thereby confirming the occurrence of the reaction. Structures of α -vanadium bronzes are very similar to V₂O₅, because of the accomodation of added metal ions in tunnels of V₂O₅ matrix without disturbing the network. However, phases with 0.1 \leq x \leq 0.15 give a diffraction pattern (Table 1), comparable with those of other β -vanadium bronzes, M_xV₂O₅ (M=Li, Na, Cu, Ag, etc)⁸⁻¹⁰. The observed diffraction lines are indexable on the basis of a monoclinic unit cell with the cell dimensions a=15.40, b=3.65, c=10.16 Å and β =108.5°. On the basis of X-ray diffraction data, a β -vanadium bronze structure could therefore be suggested for the bronze, La_{0.1}V₂O₅.

TABLE 1—X-RAY DIFFRACTION DATA OF La_{0.1}V₂O₅

d obsd (Å)	d calcd. (Å)	hkl
3.264 (s)	3.265	210
2.992 (m)	2.984	302
2.748 (w)	2.754	112
2.491 (s)	2.496	304
2.263 (vw)	2.264	104
2.152 (w)	2.143	213
2.007 (w)	2.010	014
1.829 (w)	1.825	020
1.669 (s)	1.670	322
1.578 (m)	1.573	421
1.456 (s)	1.455	024
1.345 (m)	1.346	125
1.272 (vw)	1.273	804
1.137 (w)	1.138	033
	1.137	333
1.084 (w)	1.084	434
1.026 (w)	1.026	535

* Indexed on the basis of a monoclinic cell with a=15.40, b=3.65, c=10.16 Å and β =108.5°

In La_xV₂O₅ phases, one would expect that lanthanum atoms undergo ionization, each atom donating three electrons to the oxide network, as observed in the case of lanthanide tungsten bronzes¹³. Thus, for La_xV₂O₅, the amount of V⁴⁺ should be 3x. This is in agreement with the results obtained from chemical analysis which shows that La_{0.1}V₂O₅ consists of \sim 0.30 V⁴⁺ and \sim 1.70 V⁵⁺.

The presence of V⁴⁺ is also confirmed by magnetic susceptibility and EPR data. The effective magnetic moment, μ_{eff} of La_{0.1}V₂O₅ at room temperature per mole of V⁴⁺ in the bronze is 1.74 BM which corresponds closely to the "spin only" value required for one unpaired electron. This is also consistent with the results obtained from chemical analysis. The line-width (190 G) of the EPR signal at room temperature and the g value (1.961) are characteristic of V⁴⁺ ions in oxide lattices and compare favourably with the corresponding value of Li- and Na-vanadium bronzes¹⁶.

Fig. 1. Electrical conductivity and Seebeck coefficient of La_{0.1}V₂O₅
A—Log(T) vs 1/T B—x vs T

Electrical transport measurements on La_{0.1}V₂O₅ reveal an n-type semiconducting behaviour. The conductivity, measured by the 4-probe method on the pelletised sintered polycrystalline sample in the temperature range 300-700°K shows that the conductivity is associated with an activation energy of 0.22 eV (Fig. 1). The electrical conductivity at room temperature is \sim 10⁻² ohm⁻¹ cm⁻¹. The Seebeck coefficient at room temperature is around -45 μ V/°K. The charge carrier concentration is calculated from Seebeck coefficient, α , using the expression².

$$\alpha = -198 \log \left(\frac{N-x}{x} \right)$$

where x is the number of polarons per unit cell volume and N, the number of available sites for the polarons, is obtained from

$$N = \frac{5}{3} - \frac{2}{3}x$$

This gives a value of 9×10^{20} electrons per cc of the bronze. The Seebeck coefficient remains constant from 370 to 600°K (Fig. 1) indicating constancy of charge carrier concentration over this temperature range. This permits application of the small polaron model^{2,17-19}, according to which, the electrical conductivity σ and mobility μ of a single carrier system, such as, vanadium bronzes, are given by

$$\sigma \approx (ne^2 a^2 / kT) \exp(-E/kT),$$

$$\text{and } \mu = (ea^2 / kT) \exp(-E/kT)$$

where n is the charge carrier concentration and a, the jump-distance of the hopping mechanism. Since n is essentially constant, any activation energy associated

with conductivity σ could be due only to the thermally activated mobility of the charge carriers. In such cases, a plot of $\log(\sigma T)$ versus $1/T$ will be linear as has, indeed, been observed experimentally (Fig. 1). The activation energy (0.22 eV) deduced from the plot is, however, higher than the value usually reported (~ 0.1 eV) for alkali vanadium bronzes^{3,4,19}, though in certain cases, like $(\text{NH}_4)_x\text{V}_2\text{O}_5$, similar large value (~ 0.3 eV) has been obtained¹². The comparatively high resistivity and activation energy presumably have their origin in the grain boundary effects inherent in the polycrystalline nature of the sample employed in the present work.

Acknowledgement

One of us (T.P.) is thankful to the CSIR (India) for the award of a research fellowship. Financial support provided from PL-480 Funds under contract No. NBS (G)-135 with the National Bureau of Standards, Washington, D. C., U.S.A., is gratefully acknowledged.

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